

THE TROPE OF HOME IN NEW NIGERIAN DIASPORIC NOVELS: A STUDY OF *FOREIGN GODS INC.*

Clement Tayo Abegunde

Senior Lecturer, Department of English and Communication,
Kwara State Polytechnic, Ilorin.
clementayo2011@gmail.com

Abstract

Migration is not just a common feature in new literatures from Africa. It is an experience that affects the lives of postcolonial writers who have migrated from African countries to Europe and America. This paper explores the trope of “home” in these new novels with emphasis on Okey Ndibe’s Foreign Gods Inc. Though usually conceived as a path to greener pastures, migration in modern African novels often presents the greener pastures as illusion thus bringing to the fore the writers’ quest for that home they left behind. The paper adopts postcolonial theory as theoretical framework. This approach was chosen to allow for comparison between the home and the new settlements. The study reveals that there is always a return, both physically and psychologically, to the home. The home is seen as centre of solutions to myriads of problems like marriage, homelessness, unemployment, poverty and so on, faced by the hero, Ike. His wretched house in New York is compared to the spacious house in the village, Utonki. His failed marriage always brings back memories of his aborted courtship. He sees the village god, Ngene, as his sure path to wealth. Ironically, his hope is dashed when he discovered the god would not provide him his unfathomable wealth. The paper concludes that life in the diaspora is life in the middle. The hope in the new world and the home, both at the homeland and diaspora are uncertain.

Keywords: *Diaspora, Exile, Home, Postcolonial subject, and migration*

Introduction

The word ‘exile’ has become central in every global discourse ranging from Sociology, Economics to Literature. Most of the theses on this topic have addressed reasons why people desire or decide to leave their places

of abode to sojourn in another land and end up as migrants, slaves, displaced/refugees or seeking for asylum from persecution. Literature, as imitation of reality, has been loud in the discussions of exile in the weird world where the modern man is always kept on the move to confront, or offer solutions to problems like famine, identity crisis, persecution, war, etc. Literature that interrogates this transnational existence is christened “migrant literature” as these works are produced by writers who migrate from their nations of origin (homeland) to the present country of residence.

In most post-independent African states, the pre-independence hope has been met with disappointment among its population. The case of Nigeria is an example. The socio-political reality of the post-independent Nigeria has offered nothing to cheer about. Economic and social life is in moribund. The rich are fast languishing on the brink of poverty. Cases of war, insecurity and political persecution are on the rise every day. These and other problems that nearly defy solutions have forced many populace to embrace exile to the Western countries in the search for the better life. A body of literatures produced by these exiled Nigerian writers are tagged “Nigerian diaspora literature” (Feldner, 2021). Through the creative thrust of these Nigerian writers different images reflecting migrants experiences and creatively illustrate the complexities of straddling different worlds are projected.

This body of literatures is getting more attentions than before with the idea of homeland becoming more germane in world literatures irrespective of the migrant status of the writers. Krisnaswamy (1995) contends “it is precisely as spokespersons for the dislocated and the disenfranchised that postcolonial immigrant intellectuals have gained legitimacy in the international media-market” (p. 126). Writers are not just concerned about the narration of the homeland, they also build their themes around identities and other different perspectives. But the uniqueness of their works resonates in their vivid presentation of a “home” from which they are dislocated and a milieu they strive to be re-integrated into. Akeh (2006) has this to say about these writers and their connections to the place(s) they call home(s):

Younger Nigerian writers abroad are fiercely independent individuals who, however, also long to belong somewhere and experience the

certainty and comfort of home The evidence is that this diasporic ambiguity of catering for two locations is processed through several stages of engagement and/or disengagement...though they may become increasingly internationalist in their outlook, utterances and work. Some do become home-obsessives, operating a rather more conflicted subjectivity than may be evident, full of contradictory resolutions and representations. This position of the 'poor' writer abroad is, for the most part, governed by a distanced, sensitivity managed and changeable commitment to home (pp. 14-15).

Prominent among these writers are Chimamanda Adichie, Sefi Atta, Chika Ochonu, Okey Ndibe Helen Oyeyemi, Segun Afolabi to mention but few. Home has been a recurrent trope in their works in one way or the other.

The mobility of humans has been made easy by what Atilade (2021) describes as "the global collapse of space, time and distance occasioned by technology and postmodernism" (p. 43). Unlike in the 70s and 80s, transnational borders are fluid. All it takes to move across the world is to get the passport of the intended country of destination and the means of transportation is available. Though exile provides relief from myriads of concerns the exilic subjects try to escape from, the tribulations of exile undermine most of the perceived gains (Senayon 2007). One of the tribulations exiles experience is the lack or absence of a place to call "home", a situation Kaman Brathwaite, himself an exilic writer in Britain, refers to as 'rootlessness' (Brathwaite 1999). The allure of the new home does not end the search for the better life as the hearts of the exiles continually long for the home.

The nature of the traffic shows that movements of the diasporic subjects depend on the former connections long established between the former colonies and the centre. Citizens from a former colonial states often move from their countries to a former countries that colonised their states. Ashcroft, Griffith and Tiffen (2002) assert that "more than three quarters of the people living in the world today have had their lives shaped by the experience of colonialism (p. 1). They add that "Literature offers one of the most important ways these perceptions are expressed and it is in their writing and through other arts... that day-to-day realities experienced by colonised people have been most powerfully encoded." According to

them, literature offers the ways most of these experiences/perceptions are depicted through the colonised arts and other writings. It is worthy to note that Nigerians are among the “more than three quarters” that Ashcroft et al refer to (Dickson and Egbita 2019).

This paper examines the concept of home in Okay Ndibe’s *Foreign God Inc.* within the purview of postcolonial theory. The paper follows the major character and the other supporting casts as they traverse the space between New York and other locations and localities in Nigeria without establishing a specific place as home.

Literature Review

‘Diaspora’ has become a household term in Humanity scholarship. The origin of the word is traceable to the Jewish migration experience in the biblical days (Senayon, 2007, Cohen 2008, and Farist, 2010). (Faist 2010, p. 9). Cohen (2008) asserts that the concept “originates in the composite verb *dia* and *speirein*, namely ‘to scatter’, ‘to spread’ or ‘to disperse’ (p. 18). While the origin of diaspora and discourses generated by it remains in Jewish religious history, it presently transcends it. Cohen’s study reveals that diaspora is enabled by the process of migration. He categorised diaspora into the following groups with each deriving its significance from a voluntary or forced movement from homeland: Victim diasporas, Labour diasporas, Trade diasporas; Imperial diasporas and deterritorialised diasporas (Cohen, 2008). It has been frequently used to denote religious or national groups living outside an (imagined) homeland in the contemporary time. The proliferation of meanings of diaspora in the contemporary time has prompted Krishnaswamy to warn writers against use of “politically charged words such as “diaspora” and “exile” as such use empty them of their histories of pain and suffering and are being deployed promiscuously to designate a wide array of cultural phenomenon” (p. 128). However, Sheffer (2003) affirms that the new emergence of interests generated by diasporas and its significance in contemporary times in relating modern dispersions do not extricate the concept of diaspora from its rootedness in the distant past. He attributes the proliferation of meaning of diaspora to the diversity and receptiveness associated with it presently. Aware of the diverse application of the term in the contemporary times, Sheffer (2003) decides to narrow his application of the term to include ethno-nationals:

Diaspora is a social-political formation, created as a result of either voluntary or forced migration, whose members regard themselves of the same ethno-national origin and who permanently reside as minorities in one or several host countries. Members of such entities maintain regular or occasional contacts with what they regard as their homelands and with individuals and groups of the same background residing in other host countries (p. 9-10).

Sheffer lays emphasis on the permanent nature of the migration from state of ethno-national origins and the formation of settlements in other countries that results in migrants living and emphasizing their distinctions as minorities in the host communities. Those differences are brought from a particular location/homeland and they come with some political and social implications.

In his study on diaspora and transnationalism, Faist (2010) proposes three characteristics of diaspora situation for a better understanding of the term and provides its changing meanings in the same work. The first characteristic focuses on the causes of migration in which the older notion of migration connotes forced dispersal as witnessed by the Jews while the new notions refer to any kind of dispersal including trade diaspora. The second characteristic, as he explains, is based on cross-border experiences of homeland with destination (p. 12). The older notion emphasises a return to an imagined homeland either physically or by embarking on projects to influence a country's future from abroad. The third characteristic concerns the incorporation or integration of migrants and minorities into the countries of settlement. The older notions of 'diaspora' "implied that its members do not fully integrate socially" as the majority in the new place always find ways of asserting own homeland, leading to discrimination and other social deprivation of the migrants. Despite the seeming incompatibility between the older and the newer interpretations of diaspora, it is however, clear that there is a connection to a place called "home" by diaspora subjects even when the definition and description of such term have become solidly fluid due to migratory conditions and globalisation.

The terms 'exile' and 'diaspora' are always associated with dislocation and belonging. These two concepts have become significant in migration

of individuals across international borders from their nations of origin. As the movements progress, so there is increase in dislocation and the migrants become strangers (otherness) which prompts the migrants to crave for sense of a place. Dislocation in migrant literature entails displacement and uprooting of individuals from their place of origin and the complex corollaries that follow. Krishnawasmy (1995) describes dislocation as an involving process with many possibilities. She opines that “dislocation actually opens up an abundance of alternative locations, allowing the individual to own several different homes by first becoming homeless” (p. 139). She also suggests that the process of dislocation could appear in multiple ways - temporal, spatial and linguistic. Akeh (2006) sees dislocation as some sort of alienation from home. He affirms that dislocation is integral aspect of the creating process of migrating because dislocation means “uprootedness” that comes with a “frayed sense of certainty and communal loyalty (p. 4).

Where there is dislocation, there is always belonging because the two concepts move is complementarity. Belonging refers to a sense of place which the migrant longs for as a result of being dislocated from his previous location (homeland). It involves some coping strategies devised by the migrant to survive the stress of dislocation. Inglis (2010) asserts that belonging could entail an individual identifying one or several places, people or a mixture of all these. Sometimes some migrants carry along materials from their homeland. A migrant in Scotland said she survives her longing for her homeland by cooking her homeland dishes for her family. Complexities associated with these two phenomenon are non-negotiable in these new Nigerian novels.

‘Home’ in a layman’s definition is a place where people live or where domestic activities take place. In diaspora study, there is more to home than this and so a prescriptive definition may not be enough to fully capture what a home means to an exile. According to Atilade (2021), globalisation has almost made it impossible to give accurate definition of ‘home’ for a postcolonial subject because the term allows writers to take part in events that take place in distant environment. Literature and the new order make this possible. In his words, for “such writers to say one place is a home becomes conflicting” (p. 45).

The significance of home to writers of African descent cannot be over-emphasised. Mchleod (cited in Atilade, 2021) asserts that “to be at home is to occupy a location, where we are welcome, where we can be with people very much like ourselves” (p. 44). Clifford (1994) affirms that a strong attachment to and desire for literal return to a well preserved homeland (p. 305) is one of the important features of a diasporic experience. Ray’s (2014) question: “can we attribute a single home/homeland to a diasporic subjective experience?” becomes more poignant when we explore what constitutes a home in postcolonial context. Walters (cited in Atilade, 2021) opines that the notion of home in diaspora “can represent multiple, plurilocal, constructed location of home, thus avoiding ideas of fixity, boundedness, and nostalgic exclusivity traditionally implied by the word home” (p. xvi). This is to say the definition of home in diasporic study is not fixed.

Atilade’s (2021) attempt at defining home in a recent study is commendable. He asserts that home can be defined in a diasporic situation at three levels – micro, macro and global levels. At the micro level, we see home as a residence where a person, people or family/household members live together. “It is a family or group of people that lives together” (p. 47). Home at the macro level invokes the notion of birth place, where a person was born/raise or where one’s sense of belonging lies. “it refers to hometown, village or place of origin where one originates or based (p. 47). At the global level, home becomes synonymous with home land, nation, a community of people of mainly common descent, history, and language (p. 47). Atilade believes that before we call a place home, it must be a place where “a person can find refuge and safety and live in security”. According to him, it is what could be called “comfort zone” or what Gaston Bachelard, a French phenomenologist, referred to as “*espace henreuse*” (felicitous space). Thus, defining a home becomes more complex when we realise that no place fulfills all these realities for diasporic characters as demonstrated in most Nigerian diasporic fictions.

The home then becomes a static concept which traditionally connotes a place where our ancestors used to live, a place of origin in which people define their identity according to their roots (Heckman 2006). McLeod argues in this sense that “the concept of home often performs an important function in our lives. It can act as valuable means of orientation by giving

us a sense of our place in the world. It tells us where we originated from and where we belong” (p. 211). Most Nigerian diasporic novelists and their protagonists fall into this category as home in Nigeria is a mental construction and a nationalist representation. They live in the Western countries but “divide their time and storytelling attention between the United States, the United Kingdom, and Nigeria. Accordingly, it is not surprising that two dominant areas of concern in their literatures are experiences of migration and diaspora, on the one hand, and representations of Nigeria, on the other hand (Fiedner 2019, p. 2). They are torn between allegiance to their root and loyalty to the new home. None of the two poles could be envisioned as the real home at the end. Of the two poles neither provides for them the idyllic fulfilment and succour which the home provides - home is neither here nor there (Gunter, 1981, p. 13).

The Trope of Home in Okey Ndibe’s *Foreign Gods Inc.*

One of the most thrilling aspects of Ndibe’s novel is the fact that the impact of globalisation is not only felt by humans, the gods who appears in the image of statues are not left out as they become commodified in the globalised age. As Gruel, the owner of the arts gallery, Foreign Gods Inc. claims, “a god must travel or die” (p. 2). The novel has its protagonist, Ike, a graduate of Economics from American university. He cannot secure employment because he has accent. He ekes out a living by driving taxi. His meagre earning cannot sustain him because of his expensive wife, bills and his addicted gambling lifestyle. He is wallowing in this confusion until his friend, Jonathan Falla introduces him to a multinational business outfit, Foreign God Inc., where statues of ancient gods from different regions of the globe are traded. He begins to hatch a plan to steal Ngene, a warrior god of his village, and transport it to United States to be sold to the art gallery. Through this, he thought, he would become a big man and multimillionaire who would be respected in his native land and his new home. He travels to his village, Utonki, by raising loan from his friends to steal the revered statue. He succeeds in the crime but it was not as financially rewarding as he thought. He goes back to the gallery to retrieve the statue. In his hallucination he witnesses the presence of the statue in his room which demonstrates the god’s anger against his crime of desecrating the god of Utonki.

Europe and the United States have long been viewed as asylums from poverty and suffering, places where dreams are transformed to fulfillment. In an interview conducted after publishing the novel, Okey Ndibe has this to say about the United States: “The United States is a truly extraordinary address, a place where – pardon the cliché – dreams are constantly inspired, born and nurtured.” The novel itself is a piece of Ndibe’s personal experience of his disillusionment about America as a dreamland like his protagonist as revealed in the interview.

Ike got to the United States with one ambition - to be successful after graduating from the university. His aim was to become successful as the host community is viewed as a land of equality and opportunity. The opposite happens when he is turned down from employers because of his accent. The phrase “you have an accent” can suddenly and lastingly take on a certain defining gravity (Ndibe 2019 np). In the precarious situation, the disappointment brings about frustration and desperation. As a graduate, he becomes a cab driver. The frustrations lead him to taking to drunkenness and gambling, which swallow substantial part of his income. The United States is certainly not home at the moment for him. There must be a search for another home, though not his place of origin. His host country has failed to give him any of the privileges that the home has to offer. Despite being educated in the system with near perfect certification, the same system does not see him as its citizen. He is viewed as an alien. Hence, he is not be offered employment:

His quest had started in 1997, a few months before graduation. He had applied for a job at two banks, but when he phoned one bank’s human resources department, a female employee called back and left a tense message on his voice mail: “sir” the woman said, “BayBank does not interview aliens unless they produce evidence of authorisation to work in the US”/He has to have his green card to get job (p. 67)

This encounter actually is another confirmation of his alienation. America is not his home. To put an end to his alienation, he decides to fix a pretentious marriage with a citizen. But he is duped in the process. He settles for Benita after his proposed marriage to Penny is rejected by Penny’s parents who are Black Americans. Despite their racial connection, Penny’s parents reject Ike’s marriage proposal to their

daughter because they prefer Penny marrying to a “fellow Black American man.” But his impatience also works against him as Penny would later get married to a Senegalese. His marriage to Benita is out of his freewill based on the pressure to get green card and employment in corporate firms. His intention is also defeated as he could not achieve any of these in the marriage. Instead the marriage cost him his life savings and brings with it frustration. The frustration leads him to gambling which sinks deeper into more frustrations:

He took off on a gambling junket, not to Atlantic City, this time, but to Foxwoods Resort Casino in Connecticut. He couldn't resist the Casino's special offer of double-bed rooms for twenty-three dollars (plus tax), complimentary drinks thrown in. After a weekend of binged gambling, he left the casino in sour spirits, dazed, and broke. (p. 63)

According to Atilade (2019), the diasporic characters “often experience discrimination in their host country and the only way to deal with this is to idealise their home country and to see their host country as a temporary residence even when they have spent most of their lives in the host country.” (p. 48). Ike's posture shows he does not believe there is a home anywhere. In his own case, he does not see Nigeria as his home. Hardly does he take time to think about his village or its people except to complain about his mother and sister who pester him with demands which he fails to attend to. The only time he becomes preoccupied with is when he sees Ngene as his assess to financial fortune.

Benita's ceaseless demands for money for shopping affect Ike in two ways. First, it pressures Ike to forget about his pursuit of green card. Second, it forces him to abandon his responsibility to his mother. For four years, he fails to send his mother's stipend. In the novel it is revealed that Benita marries Ike for sex only as the novel suggests. Her demand for sex is uncontrollable: “it seems that Benita wants to acquire her own in-house sex service” (p. 24). She always demands for sex and whenever Ike refuses, she accuses him of infidelity:

Bernita harped at him about sex. She is enraged when fatigued after long hours behind the wheel, he made a quick job of it. If he never said he wasn't up to it, she became even more furious. She harangued with charges of infidelity. “You're chasing after bitches”, she'd rail each time

he was tired. Cause I don't mean I don't know some white bitch got you all crazy and lost. (33)

The western notion of marriage is also contrasted with the traditional marriage. Benita and Ike's marriage represents the western marriage value where women occupy focal position. In case of divorce, western women receive alimony. Regina and Egoigwe stands for African traditional marriage system where women are treated as trash. Women decisions are not respected neither is there a place given to women to receive anything if the marriage collapses and divorce ensues. This is demonstrated in the dialogue between Ike and Regina when he visits Nigeria:

He did all this and you stayed with him, Ike said.

You speak as if you're not from these parts as if you don't know how difficult it is for a woman to get up and leave her husband.

The scandal, the evil eyes cast on you by your own family and others. The rumors that the man must have sent you home because he caught you with a lover. I had to stay. (p. 224)

Women have to endure marital stress and sometimes beatings in order to avoid the stigma of divorce and being thrown back to her father's compound like stones. A man must not die before his wife. If this happens, the wife is accused of witchcraft and held responsible. The widow has no right to sue the husband's family for maltreatment. The conversation does not portray Ike as a true son of Utonki. He has been immersed into Western ideology and aligned himself to American philosophy of marriage and legal system forgetting that he is part of the African system where justice for women is elusive. Ike is between the two dominant poles, neither here nor there. He is ostracised in America and he does not belong to his root.

His journey from US to Nigeria throws us into series of intrigues right from the airport to his village. The author arguably uses Ike's homecoming to reveal substantially the ills in Nigeria both at micro and macro levels. He begins to encounter problems from Nigeria's corrupt law enforcement official's right within the airports perimeter and outside. The

determination of the Nigeria Custom and Nigeria Police Force to extort money from Ike is the starting point. The Custom official on duty questions him about his luggage with demand for bribe. The scene portrays the synergy among the officials as other officials join the front man in the demand. The official questions Ike on why he has so large luggage:

You have twenty- two packet shirts, twelve dresses, many, many trinkets and sixteen deodorants.

Ike nodded.

That na commercial quantity. You have to pay duty.

What do you mean by commercial quantity?

Na buying and selling.

It's not true. Ike looked straight in the face.

They are gifts

The officer sneered. Gifts? He sharply turned away.

The officer shrugged, unimpressed. I don't tell you. This na commercial quantity... (p. 75)

The officials are driven by the general attitudes of Nigerian officials to make quick wealth through extortions and abuse of power and privileges. They are involved in abuse of office through bribery and corruption. The police mount road blocks to extort money from cab drivers and their passengers. The narrator informs the readers:

You think I be twenty-naira Police? Ejoo bring correct money. Otherwise come down! Backed a burly man in a police uniform. Ike made to speak but held back. “De passenger na VIP” the driver said, his voice veiled caution to the officer. Which kin VIP no get him own Mercedes Benz? VIP dey take taxi? Don't waste my time. Oya, multiply by two and go. The driver added another twenty – naira note, and they were waved on. Ike hissed. The driver restarted the music. (p. 85)

Refusal to give bribe or play according to the officers rule of engagements often brings with it delays and frustration. Reactions from these officials are depicted by the author through the use of pidgin which unofficially the language of most law enforcement agencies in Nigeria. Ike is reluctant and objects to offering bribe to the officials as he castigates them.

On his way back to America, Ike was no more reluctant to offer bribe because of his illegal possession of Ngene. He has to bargain with the custom officer on duty and the latter maximises the opportunity to demand huge amount:

*Oya bring one thousand, the man officer said. He frowned up. I no wan waste more time. Ike cast a sideward glance at the huddle of officers and saw the 'wench' wagging her fingers at the statue.
'Five hundred' he offered.
Mustachioed officer glowered at him.
You tink sey na joke I come here come joke?
He made an exaggerated motion of turning away.
Please, Ike pleaded. I'll make it six hundred. (pp. 290 – 291)*

He has no choice other than to succumb when the officer threatens to call other officer to check his luggage. He has to comply at the end because of “the fortune that awaited him once the statue made it to New York” (p. 291).

The life of Egoigwe addresses another dimension to corruption in Nigeria at the micro-level. Egoigwe has amassed monumental wealth through drug dealing. He is celebrated by the society despite all the crimes he commits. Ike's politician friend who also displays a similar wealth shows the political class as arbiter of corruption as the masses are left to suffer and feed on the crumbs that fall from the politicians' tables. Both men go spiritual by employing pastors, dibia, alfas for spiritual protection and success in the ugly dealings. The author uses those instances to describe how deep corruption and craze for wealth have eaten the society. Like these men, Ike is not different in the desperation to be rich and the import he attaches to riches. He is back in Utonki to steal the village god, Ngene. He is also desperate to become a US citizen by bribing to arrange marriage with a Puerto Rican citizen.

His entrance into Utonki speaks volume about his alienation from his place of birth. He enters the village quietly unnoticed. No pomp and pageantry to welcome him as it is done to sojourners who returned from the United States back 'home'. No wonder he does not see himself as part of the village. His mother and sister, Nkiru, are not aware of his coming.

He sneaks into the village like an alien. All his focus is how to succeed in stealing Ngene. He does not belong to the traditional or the Christian sects. He shows his disinterest in both religion. His disdain for traditional religion is reflected in his statement that Ngene is no longer a war god, because “the warriors of Utonki had not fought a war in more than hundred years” (p. 5). His return to Utonki certainly needs more explanation.

Though the visit was to abscond with Ngene to United States when he leaves the village, the author briefly uses Ike’s visit to give insight through flashback to Ike’s youthful/adolescent age when there were conflicts between worshippers of Ngene and the Christians in the Orthodox Church planted and defended by Rev. Stanton. Before the sudden appearance of Rev. Stanton on the bank of the village river, Ngene was the only object of worship. It was always dependable in battles against external forces. But the arrival of the Rev changed the religious terrain of Utonki just as in Achebe’s *Things Fall Apart*. Stanton’s arrival fragmented the people of Utonki as they become polytheistic in their religious dedication. Welcoming Rev Stanton in the market “square where the community celebrated their festivities is symbolic, it announces the dispute of the space which absolutely belonged to Ngene before. The defeat of Utonki’s warrior by Stanton’s foretells the fate that would befall the community and their god. That was a boost for his god and minus for the traditional religion.

If Stanton’s arrival was a blow to the traditional worship, the arrival of Pastor Uka and his firebrand Pentecostal worship is a harder one. His self-acclaimed ability to prophecy and see into the unknown world makes many of the villagers, which include Ike’s family and the Pastor tries as much as possible to con Ike but he refuses to be conned. The new church demonstrates the new brand of Christianity that modernity has brought to Nigerians who are in pursuit of prosperity and freedom from enemies. In the end they become victims of their so-called men of God represented in Uka.

Atilade (2021) affirms that in most postcolonial diasporic writings, the traditional definition of home as a static concept has been problematised by the experiences of the characters defined as postcolonial subjects. For most of them who are still living within the geographical location of their

origin, the realities of this home negate this conventional and static concept and thus force them to begin to have mental construction of their own ideal space and long for a place where they can call “home”. However, the uprooted subjects have a home that they construct or imagined after they, like Ike, realise that their ideal home is not realisable. That home might not be physical. It could be in an ideology or religion or other realities that provides them their desire like riches or change of status. All his hope for that desired home is sustained on his successful sale of Ngene. He dreams of becoming rich after disposing Ngene in Gruels’ gallery. That state is where he hopes to get warm, shelter and whatever love the world has for him. He exudes the confidence as for the first time he felt he’d truly returned from Utonki. “The city was there before his eyes. “It was there in more than one sense. There-for him. Strangely-considering all his old grouse against the city-he felt comforted to be back. His heart swelled with the satiety of a man about to reach out and touch his dreams.” That dream does not depend on the location but on wealth and riches. The ‘home’ for him is neither New York nor Utonki (Nigeria).

Conclusion

This paper has explored the different circumstances that project the idea of home in the novel. The literature reviewed in the paper clearly gives different perspectives of what constitutes home in diasporic situation. By portraying Ike as an immigrant who neither belongs to the society in America nor his village in Utonki, the novelist makes it known to us that his characters do not really see anywhere as home whether at micro, macro or global levels. This conclusion is justified by the protagonist’s inability to be part of the societies thus becoming alienated to both his homeland and his host community. He exists beyond the boundaries of institutions constructing his own idea of home in becoming wealthy through the successful sale of Ngene. The home becomes a hallucination for him as that dream becomes elusive.

Works Cited

- Akeh, A. (2006) Poor African writers travelling: Home and exile in younger Nigerian diasporic writing. *Sentinel poetry*, 48.
- Ashcroft, B., Griffiths, G. and Tiffin, H. (2002) *The empire writes back*. London and New York: Routledge.

The Trope of Home in New Nigerian Diasporic Novels – Abegunde

- Atilade, K.A. (2021) Globalisation and the concept of home in Tahar Ben Jelloun's Migrant novels. In O. Coker and A. Adeniran (Eds) *Texts and Contexts of migration in Africa and Beyond*, (pp. 43-56) Austin Texas: PanAfrican University Press
- Brathwaite, K. (1999) *ConVERSations with Nathaniel Mackey*. Staten Island and Minneapolis: WE Press and XCP: Cross Cultural Poetics.
- Cohen, R. (2008) *Global diasporas: An introduction* (2nd ed). London: Routledge.
- Coker, O. and Adeniran (2019) (Eds) *Texts and Contexts of migration in Africa and beyond*, Austin Texas: Pan African University Press
- Dickson, B. and Egbuta, C (2019) Migration, maturation and identity crises in Chris Abani's selected novels: A postcolonial reading. In A. Tilbe, M. Rahn and R. Khalil (Eds) *Culture, literature and migration* (pp. 154-177). London: Transnational Press.
- Faist, T and Baubuck, R (2010) *Diaspora and transnationalism: concepts, theories and methods*, Amsterdam University press
- Feldner, M. (2019) *Narrating the new African diaspora: 21st century Nigerian literature in context*. Austria: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Gurr, Andrew. 1981. *Writers in Exile: The Identity of Home in Modern Literature*. Sussex: The Harvesters Press; New Jersey: Humanities Press.
- Heckmann, C. (2006) *Concepts of Home and Belonging in Postcolonial Literature compared in the novels "Small Island" by Andrea Levy and "White Teeth" by Zadie Smith*. Munich: GRIN Publishing: 2006.
- Krishnaswamy, R. (1995) Mythologies of migrancy: Postcolonialism, Postmodernism and the politics of (dis)location. *Ariel: A review of international English literature* pp. 125-146.
- Ndibe, O. (2014) *Foreign god inc*. New York: Soho Press.
- Senayon, O. (2007) From local to global: A critical survey of exile experience in recent African poetry. *Nebula*, 4: 2, 223-252.
- Sheffer, G. (2003) *Diaspora politics at home abroad*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.